

Research

A new application for PLC in smart factory by wireless technology

Islam Mohammad Saiful¹, MD Fazle Rabbi², Prof. Zhang Jiabo^{3*}

¹Communication and Information System, Chongqing University of Posts and Telecommunications, China

²Mechanical Design and Manufacturing and Automation, Chongqing university of posts and telecommunications, China

³Information and Communication Engineering, Chongqing University of Posts and Telecommunications, china

***Corresponding author**

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Abstract: Technical advancement in the industry has changed the lives of people directly in last few decades. Industrial revolution has contributed significantly to this change. Whether it is the matter of mass production, safety, or other social aspects like social economy and jobs for humans, it has affected everyday life. People are again expecting major changes in the industrial automation. The new generation of revolution that is supposed to start in next few years (tentatively 2020) has given the name Industry 4.0. Researchers and engineers are constantly. Focusing to make the smart devices and systems to support this concept. This industrial era is expected to embrace cyber-physical systems containing smart devices as its components and with the industrial internet of things (IIOT). This documents talks about an attempt to automate a simple paper rolling machine using Siemen's S7-1200 processor and the HMI developed. The second section is about using the new platform to develop dynamic HMI that can assist to implement the concept of Industry 4.0. Literature review discusses about some of the transactions papers and other papers in renowned journals which talks about the concept, design principles, and aspects of the next generation of industrial revolution. Towards the end, the document has the results of the projects, some discussions, conclusions, and then some recommendations for future development of the project.

Keywords: PLC, HMI, Automation, MIMO, Industry 4.0

Modern Control Systems

In general, there are two major divisions of control theory viz. classical control theory and modern control theory [6]. In classical control theory the system is analyzed in time domain using differential equation or frequency domain using Laplace Transform. And systems are

limited to single input single output systems (SISO) most of the time. On the other hand, state space tools are used to analyze systems in modern control theory and can deal with multiple inputs multiple output systems (MIMO). Similarly, regarding the flow of control signal there are two common types viz. feedback control and sequence control. Feedback control is the process of controlling the input parameters using a controller which is actuated by a signal that compares the measured value with desired value (which is a previous set point). Sequence control is a process in which the system performs various actions based on a fixed sequence or logic based on various system states. Also, there is a third type of practice in automation field that is based on the concept of hysteresis. It can be used for pressure switches, speed controls, and other areas where the smooth operation is desired. The approach of industrial/process control and automation was different few decades ago. Most of the control systems before 1950s were analog types. They had switches, contractors, relays, timers, and counters and the main purpose of such control circuit was to turn on and off the machines/processes. The first digital control system put into operation was in 1959 at Port Arthur (Texas)[6]. Then, some specialized computers capable of offering direct digital control appeared in the late 1960s. However, they were very expensive and as a result could not sustain in the market for long. The multipurpose, smaller sized, and cheap microcomputers were introduced in the industry at early 1970s and they rapidly overtook the existing market and are predominant still today.

Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs)

Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs) are the small digital computers used in modern days control applications. They are flexible to program according to users need and are capable of generating control signals that can control machines and processes in industry.

As discussed above, industries back in 1960s had expensive electric/electronic control circuits offering limited uses and less flexibility. Automotive industries were at the top of manufacturing industries during that period. But they were having cost challenges as it would cost a lot to manufacture and assemble the various parts and the whole automobile. Though computers were an option to boost the manufacturing and assembling process, they were big in size. Engineers were facing challenges to use those big sized computers in the plant. They were actively seeking for a better option but there were many challenges to replace the existing technology. People were used to with the prevailing control circuits using relays and counters. Also, the circuits

were easier to understand and implement. There were already thousands of engineers, electricians, machine operators, and technical workers in industry.

Embracing the new technology replacing the well accepted existing technology could have a negative impact on production efficiency. Against all these odds, designers succeeded to make a small sized device which could function like computers while embracing existing relay ladder like logic. These became the Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) of today. Despite many positive sides of these devices, they were still very expensive to use for average user. Also, there were lots of people in the manufacturing industry who took time to be convinced that PLCs were reliable and trustworthy as previous relay circuits. With continuous improvements and modifications, it took many years for the PLC to be well accepted and financially sound.

Definition: National Electric Manufacturers Association (NEMA) has defined PLC as: Programmable Logic Controller(PLC) is a digital electronic apparatus with a programmable memory for storing instructions to implement specific function such as logic, sequencing, timing, counting, and arithmetic, to control machines and processes. Looking at today's PLCs function, one can explain PLC as a modular device that takes multiple inputs/signals from physical system, facilitates programming (ladder logic in most of the case) to carry inspection, manipulation, and control over output signals, and output the result signals. It can communicate to I/O, to other PLCs, stores the programs and data. The connection to input and output can be carried out either by proprietary connections/networks using dedicated devices/connectors or using the general connection means like Ethernet, RS- 232, and so-on.

PLCs Functional Block Diagram

The PLC is one of the most important components of today's advanced control and automation system. The following are the main reasons that make PLCs a prime component in manufacturing and process industries:

Hardware Implementation

As mentioned in our objectives, two systems viz. paper roller using two step motors, Siemen's S7 1200 PLC and a HMI screen having admin client conjunction are developed in the lab.

Paper Roller Machine

An automated motion control architecture is demonstrated in the lab. The motion of stepper motors is controlled using Siemens S7-1200 Processor and accessing the system through an HMI screen. The processor is programmed with ladder logic (LAD) using TIA Portal V14. The program involves the general instructions to advance functional blocks. The general instructions used are bit logic operations like normally open contacts, normally closed contacts, assignment bit (output coil), timers, counters, comparators, deferent math functions, and conversion operators. The advanced instructions are the advance technology objects like built-in motion control blocks and PID Compact block. They have main role of making the program easy and short. If the program is to be designed using the traditional theoretical approach, modeling the system and designing a PID could be very dicot and time consuming. But these built in blocks have made the design portion very easy. Once used in the systems with an arbitrary (approximate) PID value, the only thing the programmer

is required is to tune the system. Then it itself ND out the accurate value of P, I, and D for the system. It is good of Siemens that there are deferent types of built in instructions for almost all ends of controls and automation. These instructions range from basic instructions to extended instructions, technology, communication, and other optional packages. The logic developed will be discussed later.

3.1.1 Working

A paper roller hardware, controlled using Siemens S7-1200 processor, is built in the lab. It demonstrates the motion control application of stepper motor. It has two stepper motors. The shafts are attached to the arm of the hardware. One arm contains the paper to roll and next arm is where the paper is to be rolled. When the system starts, the paper from the loaded arm begins to roll over the second arm. The image of the system with description of each component is described below.

Component Description

Siemen's PLC

The PLC used for this project is Siemens SIMATIC S7-1200, CPU 1214C DC/DC/DC model. It is a powerful controller with many capabilities. It has functions that can perform counting, measuring, closed-loop control, and motion control. Also, it has signal modules for expansion of controllers by input/ output channels and communication modules for expansion of controllers by communication interfaces. The processor communicates to the programming panel and other sematic controllers through the PROFINET interface. It supports TCP/IP, ISO-on-TCP, and S7 communication protocols. It is a better option for the applications where programmable controllers would not have been economically viable in the past. Talking about the mechanical features, the Siemens Sematic S7- 1200 processor is small in size and comes with rugged, compact plastic enclosure with easily accessible connection and control terminals. And it complies with the VDE, UL, CSA and FM (Class 1, Category 2; Danger zone groups A, B, C and D, T4A) standards.

All the major features and characteristics of this model are listed as below:

3.1.1 Hardware and Pictures

The following pictures are the screenshots of the project developed with their description that summarize the entire the logic developed (program), dynamics of coding, and the HMI designed. The picture below (Figure 3-4) shows that the PLC and the HMI are configured in the project and are connected through the PN/IE connection. One cyclic interrupt, three functions (FCs) and a data block are used in this program.

Figure 3-1: Device and Network

The above figure (Figure 3) shows the processor 1214C DC/DC/DC and its configuration option. The processor and other additional modules can be configured in this section. Any modules such as input, output, safety, etc. can be added to the rack if needed. Also, different version of devices can be selected through this window and different properties of device as well as Ethernet port can be set here. The typical device used here in this project is CPU 1214C DC/DC/DC 6ES7 214-1AG40-0XBO V4.1.

shows the ladder logic program written in Main [OB1]. It has basic seal circuit to start and stop the program and three FC (Function Call) blocks called as shown below:

Figure 3-2: Main Program

Figure 3-1 and Figure 3-2 show the code used in the cyclic interrupt. The reading from potentiometer is read through IW64 as shown in figure and is scaled as required. The scaled value is the input for the PID.

Figure 3-8 shows the PID Compact used in the program. It is built in function block available in TIA portal. It reads input from Input or Input PER,

Compares the value with set point and generates the output based on the result of comparison. The nature of this output depends on the PID parameters set while configuring the PID Compact block.

The output values can be obtained from Output,

Output_PER, or Output PWM.

Figure 3-3: PID Compact Block

The whole project is controlled through the HMI screens shown in Figure 3-12, Figure 3- and Figure 3-213 below. As shown in Figure 3-12, the set point for the PID, the radius of the rollers is entered from the HMI. Similarly, the direction of motion, as well as start, stop, reset command is also given through the HMI. There are tags associated with the HMI, as shown in Figure 3-14. When an instruction is given through the HMI, these tags get changed. The program is written in such a way that all the tags used inside the program have nothing to do with external tags, so that the program remains intact and can be easily copied and used in any other hardware sets. The only thing that needs to care is assign the tags from hardware sets to the corresponding tags inside the program. Here, all the HMI tags are assigned to the corresponding tags inside the program using the Assign Parameter FC. The Figure 3-9 and Figure 3-10 shows the code involved in the program for assigning parameters.

Figure 3-4: Assign Parameter2

The speed for the roller to be rolled is kept constant here. Then the speed for the roller from which the paper is rolled is calculated using the Calculation FC. It calls the calculate FC which calculate the initial velocity for the roller. Then, based on the input from potentiometer the output speed is adjusted and the adjusted speed is fed to the motor. The initial velocity for the follower roller is roughly estimated using simple gear equation:

$$R_1 * V_1 = R_2 * V_2 \text{ where,}$$

R_1 is radius of first roller

V_1 is speed of first roller

R_2 is radius of second roller

V_2 is speed of second roller

Figure 3-5: Calculate Block

Figure 3-6: Calculate Speed1

Built in Motion Control Blocks are other important components of the project designed. They can control the motor based on the pattern assigned in the technology object (To Positioning Axis here). A user can define Technology object based on the requirements. It contains the information of motion profile like the start/stop pattern, number of pulses/distances per revolution, acceleration, limiting conditions and so on. The motion control blocks used in this project are MC Power, MC Home, MC Reset, MC Move Velocity, and MC Halt. Figure 3-7, Figure 3-8, Figure 3-9 and Figure 3-10 show how the blocks are called in the program. Two axes viz. axis 1 and axis 2 are defined in this project to control the two motors. Figure 3-5 and Figure 3-6 shown below corresponds to axis 1 and Figure 3-7 and Figure 3-8 corresponds to axis 2.

Figure 3-7: Motion Control Blocks2 for axis1

Figure 3-8: Motion Control Blocks1 for axis2

Figure 3-9: Motion Control Blocks2 for axis2

User Defined Tags (UDTs) are easier way of handling Tags. They allow users to define the tags of same or different data types into a single name. User can then define any tags of the defined data type. The tag thus defined duplicates the nature of data type. It is very useful and easier to handle similar types of tags if the system has large number of similar sets of data. The good thing about the tag- based PLCs are they are easy to program. The programmer does not need any specific hardcore port or location. Instead, the programmer can define any tag and use that for intermediate use whenever and however required. It makes programming flexible as the programmer does not have to worry about the number of variable/tags constraint. But, the values those tags contain might not be used instantly. In such cases, those values need to be stored somewhere so they can be accessed from there whenever required. Data Blocks are such locations. Data block [DB1] shown below in the Roller1, Roller2, HMI, and PID tags of user defined data types Rollers Data,

HMI Data, and PID Values.

Figure 3-10: Data Block

Name	Data type	Start value	Retain	Accessible from HMI/OPC UA	Write	Visible in HMI engineering	Setpoint	Supervision	Comment
▼ Static									
▼ Roller1									
Radius	Dint	0	False	True	True	True	False		
InitialSpeed	Dint	0	False	True	True	True	False		
FinalSpeed	Dint	0	False	True	True	True	False		
▼ Motion									
Motion[0]	Bool	false	False	True	True	True	False		Power, Reset, Home, MoveVelocity, Halt respectively
Motion[1]	Bool	false	False	True	True	True	False		Power, Reset, Home, MoveVelocity, Halt respectively
Motion[2]	Bool	false	False	True	True	True	False		Power, Reset, Home, MoveVelocity, Halt respectively
Motion[3]	Bool	false	False	True	True	True	False		Power, Reset, Home, MoveVelocity, Halt respectively
Motion[4]	Bool	false	False	True	True	True	False		Power, Reset, Home, MoveVelocity, Halt respectively
▼ Direction									
Direction[0]	Bool	false	False	True	True	True	False		Forward to2, and Reverse 2to1 respectively
Direction[1]	Bool	false	False	True	True	True	False		Forward to2, and Reverse 2to1 respectively
▼ Roller2									
Radius	Dint	0	False	True	True	True	False		
InitialSpeed	Dint	0	False	True	True	True	False		
FinalSpeed	Dint	0	False	True	True	True	False		
▼ Motion									
Motion[0]	Bool	false	False	True	True	True	False		Power, Reset, Home, MoveVelocity, Halt respectively
Motion[1]	Bool	false	False	True	True	True	False		Power, Reset, Home, MoveVelocity, Halt respectively
Motion[2]	Bool	false	False	True	True	True	False		Power, Reset, Home, MoveVelocity, Halt respectively
Motion[3]	Bool	false	False	True	True	True	False		Power, Reset, Home, MoveVelocity, Halt respectively
Motion[4]	Bool	false	False	True	True	True	False		Power, Reset, Home, MoveVelocity, Halt respectively

Figure 3-11: Inside the Data Blocks1

The Figure 3-12, Figure 3-13, and Figure 3-14 below are the HMIs developed for this project. The Figure 3-12 is the main HMI screen that opens up at the beginning of the project. It has two buttons for MANUAL and AUTO selection.

Figure 3-12: HMI Main Screen

The MANUAL button can be used in the project during start of the rolling process to hold the paper tightly. When clicked on MANUAL button, it opens up the new screen as shown in Figure 3-23. It has options for moving both the motors forward and backward. The REFRESH button actually *resets* the motion blocks i.e. enables the RESET block in this program. The close button closes the screen and takes one back to the main screen.

Figure 3-13: HMI Manual Screen

When completed adjusting the paper in the hardware, the system is ready to roll paper continuously. But it needs few things to setup before that. The AUTO button takes one to the new screen. It has buttons to start the process, select the direction of motion, power/move/reset/home the motion blocks, and I/O boxes to enter the radius of rollers and set point for the PID Compact. Once an instruction is set through the HMI, the tags associated with HMI Tags get updated.

Figure 3-14: HMI Auto Screen

In the admin screen, people with administrator right can login with their user name and password. This screen has access to additional authority. For example, they can add new user, update the information of current user, etc. The user screen has all the information obtained from the plant. The tags from the PLCs are directly linked to the screen so that the user can have an idea about the real-time data from the floor. The user thus can know how the device or equipment of interest is performing. The alarm in the screen shows an error if any of the variables go outside the normal range.

Results and Discussion

Two prototypes are successfully designed in a one-year period. The paper roller is an example of how the motion of stepper motors can be controlled using Siemens S7- 1200 1214C DC/DC/DC processor through TIA Portal. The program designed is a basic program. The project developed is not an advanced project that can contribute to the current practice or technology, but is obviously a good way of demonstrating how a complex system can be easily controlled using modern

technologies. The target of the project at the beginning was to use the latest Siemens Mindshare to demonstrate the drive control and analyze how this modern technology be effective in implementing IIoT and the most awaited Industry 4.0. But, because of some problems and the time constraints the targeted objective was not achieved. But this project is definitely a start for the research in modern automation technology at the college.

The admin-user interface developed looks common and many other advanced HMI screens might be available in the market. But developing the interface using Proview DS is something different. As mentioned earlier, the software is new and is still in the development phase and cannot be found in market easily to date. But developing the interface/HMI using this software for the industrial use is very easier as compare to other existing platforms and takes less time as compare to commercially available platforms. It is mainly because accessing PLCs Tags from Proview DS is easier. Once the user get connected to a device, all the Tags can be used directly as if it is the proprietary tools. This feature makes Proview DS special in the field of HMI development. As discussed before, the HMI will have crucial role in the future industry. To address the big data from the industry the proprietary HMIs may have many problems. For example connection with other systems, connection with data cloud, etc. But Proview DS solves these problems. Any PLC can be added as a new station and then used further in the design. Since it supports cloud computing and OPC connection, it is capable of addressing most of the expectations for HMIs in the future industry.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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